

INTERNET OF THINGS IN THE MINING INDUSTRY - SECURITY TECHNOLOGIES IN THEIR APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT. The Internet of Things are essentially huge networks of connected devices that collect and share data (information) both for specific processes and their application environment. The use of the Internet of Things (IoT) is changing every industry because it allows device-to-device communication and automates the maintenance, communication, and interaction between processes and their management. IoT gives businesses real-time information on how their companies' systems work, significantly reducing labour costs. For this reason, more and more mining companies are taking advantage of the opportunities provided by IoT, creating their own networks of devices and communication environment. At the same time, IoT has become one of the most critical technologies of our century, due to the fact that cloud technologies and Wi-Fi networks, which are the basis of IoT, have become an attractive place for cyberattacks. The data collected by IoT sensors contain a huge amount of personal and company information, hence, it is especially important that they are securely stored and maximally protected. This article discusses some critically important technologies to ensure the security of IoT implementation and use in the mining industry.

Keywords: Internet of Things, mining industry, implementation, security technologies

Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) are gigantic networks of connected physical devices that collect, transmit, and share data about the environment in which they are embedded through sensors built into them (Arora, 2020). To make sharing possible, IoT provides a common platform and a common language for devices to communicate with each other.

IoT is critical to any industry because digital systems record, monitor, and correct any interactions between the connected devices, providing real-time information about the company's work.

The mass penetration of IoT in every field and its continuous development has made it a preferred but also critical technology, because it is very important that the data collected and transmitted by various sensors are sent securely to the IoT platform (Hassija et al., 2019; Arora, 2020). The security and accuracy of the information transmitted are of particular importance in the mining industry, where minimal inaccuracy in the data can lead to major adverse consequences.

Security threats in IoT applications

In addition to the standard information security problems, the IoT applications used in the industry also face specific challenges such as problems with confidentiality, authentication, encryption, management, storage of information, etc. due to the peculiarities of the IoT environment.

As is known, in every IoT environment there are four particularly important layers (Fig. 1), which are used in every IoT application (Zhou et al., 2018; Arora, 2020).

The first layer called a sensory or recognition layer is the basic level. It involves the use of different types of physical equipment – sensors and devices – that collect all kinds of information, i.e. accept the data and can perform different functions. There are different types of sensors for the perception of data types, for example for camera, smoke detection, temperature maintenance, humidity, etc. In addition, sensors can be mechanical, electrical, electronic, chemical, ultrasonic, etc., but they all register changes in the real physical environment.

The most critical threats for this layer are the sensors themselves, as there is always the possibility of a malfunction that results in the submission of incorrect data that may cause incorrect actions.

The second layer, called network, uses a communication network to transmit the collected data. Its main function is the transmission of information obtained from the sensor layer for subsequent processing and analysis.

Fig. 1. Layers in IoT environment

Since it uses different types of channels for the transmission of information, which do not always use encryption to a sufficiently reliable degree, it is always possible for the information transmitted to be intercepted and replaced with an unreliable one.

Since IoT uses different data transit technologies (depending on the type of data transmitted by different types of sensors), this makes the data in transit much more vulnerable to cyber-attacks such as DDoS, routing redirection, intercepting the real information and replacing it with fabricated data, etc.

The third layer in IoT, called middle-ware, acts as a bridge between the network and the application layer, providing powerful computational capabilities and possibilities for the permanent storage of the transmitted data. Many IoT apps use this layer to provide reliability and security of the apps themselves. It usually includes data repository, various web and cloud services.

This layer is also vulnerable to attacks on both web services and databases where the catalogued information is stored. It is susceptible to man-in-the-middle, SQL injection, flooding, etc., attacks.

The fourth, application layer directly provides functions and services to end users. Various end-to-end IoT applications such as smart grids, smart transportation, smart mines, smart cities, etc. are based in the fourth layer. In this layer, depending on the application used, there are specific security issues that are not present in the other layers. The application layer is susceptible to attacks such as data theft, access control, denial of service and privacy issues.

Hence, each of the four layers in the IoT environment has specific security issues. It is important to note that due to the heterogeneity of the information supplied by the sensors and the specific application, different gateways are located between the layers, which connect them and help the movement of data between them. These gateways also have specific data security issues.

For the most part, IoT applications use cloud services to store and retrieve data and information, and the risks caused by the cloud must be taken into account (Zhou W. et al., 2018). Cloud is a public platform used by many users and there may be malicious users who could be a threat to IoT-related data. This is an additional security challenge.

Judging from the above, ensuring the security of the IoT environment is much more challenging than providing standard information technology (IT).

Application of IoT in the mining industry and security technologies used

In the last 10 years, IoT applications have entered the industry on a large scale, being the main engine for the development of the fourth industrial revolution - Industry 4.0 (Bakhshi et al., 2018; Hassija et al., 2019). Mining companies that make huge investments in their production are also part of this development.

One of the key factors for the wide entry of IoT applications in the mining industry is related to the harsh and unfavourable working conditions. It is also important that the response time in case of emergencies in this industry is too short and thus, the workers' reaction is not always feasible.

One of the first areas in which the implementation of IoT applications in general and in the mining industry began is the so-called smart transport. All modern cars have a central computer that monitors the operation of the engine and various functions of the car through different sensors.

In the transport systems in mining companies, where the working conditions and the machines themselves are heavier than the standard ones, many different IoT applications are used.

In companies that develop opencast deposits and where transport systems are especially important, different types of sensors are built in into the dump trucks that have big capacity – from 80 to 300 tons, which monitor not only the operation of the engine but other particularly important indicators as well. Due to the peculiarities of the terrain and the weight of the machines, there are IoT applications that monitor the angle of inclination of the terrain, the pressure in the tyres, the fuel consumption on climb or descent, the distribution of the load, etc.

When developing underground deposits, IoT applications are used to monitor the volume of emitted gases, the temperature of the main nodes and the condition of the working units, the depth of drilling and other important parameters for each particular mining machine.

In the last decade, due to the harsh working conditions, remote-controlled machines have started to be used in the mining industry, with various IoT applications or trained operators to work with them – i.e. the subjectivity of the human factor is largely avoided.

In both types of deposits, the data that comes from each particular IoT application, device and smart machine is transmitted to a cloud structure where they are processed and permanently stored. On the basis of the information received, a comprehensive logistics system for the management of the equipment is created, which optimises the transport functions. Thus, the stay of the machines, the unnecessary load or collisions in the work are avoided, since the transport is only part of the overall mining process in the mining industry.

Another very important strand in the mining industry and the underground construction is the use of IoT's applications for control of the air conditioning systems and air circulation. The supply of a clean jet of air is critical in the underground development of deposits, and all their work depends on it.

In addition to powerful fans, modern ventilation systems include a large amount of sensors that analyse in real time the quality and quantity of the air flow and, depending on the parameters, can adjust it. At the same time, they are associated with the so-called ventilation barriers that are automatically activated by the relevant sensors and maintain the air quality in a given horizon, face or a specific workplace.

In the mining and underground construction industries, the sensors that control the quality and quantity of the air flow are always duplicated to ensure a high level of security. Moreover, the location of the sensors is of particular importance so that the data they collect can give an accurate and real picture of the air conditioning process.

Another area in which IoT applications in the mining industry are used is the processing of extracted minerals, where depending on its type different types of sensors monitor the process and automatically manage the addition of the necessary reagents.

The diversity of IoT applications used in the mining industry, the availability of different types of sensors and the availability of different types of communication protocols, as well as the use of Wi-Fi networks significantly hinder the security. In addition, many of the systems used in the mining industry use GPS to monitor and track transport systems or specific processes, which further complicates the problem.

Each IoT application used in the mining industry consists of a large number of different sensors and connected devices and a variety of protocols and technologies. The cost-effectiveness of IoT, the delays in transmission of information, the reliability

and security of the IoT environment must be provided already at the design stage of the IoT environment for a specific application. It is also important to anticipate its development and scale (Blyler, 2017).

The security technologies that apply to IoT applications in the mining industry can be summarised in several large groups:

Security of sensors providing data for the IoT application

All sensors and devices that transmit data and perform different functions regardless of the specific IoT application should be certified and compliant with the overall architecture. When performing functions that are critical from the point of view of the mining industry, it is obligatory for each sensor to be duplicated in order to ensure the continuity of the supplied data flow.

Periodic inspection and calibration of the sensors is necessary, as it is possible for them to fail and start transmitting incorrect data. In case of any suspicion of deviation from the usual values, it is necessary to check and validate the information supplied by the sensors. In a distributed architecture, as is usually the case in the mining industry, it is mandatory to correctly select the location of the individual sensors in order to avoid distortion of the information supplied.

IoT Authentication

A mandatory security condition in each IoT application is to include different mechanisms for authentication of devices and entities. Depending on the required level of security, the technologies used can be varied. Generated static passwords can be used for device authentication, two-factor authentication, digital certificates, and biometric data for objects and entities.

It is also necessary to use authentication in data transmission protocols, which can be implemented through digital authentication certificates, additionally linked to cryptographic protocols.

It is important to note that most of the authentication technologies used in IoT applications do not involve human intervention - i.e. the checks are carried out through M2M communication, which guarantees additional security.

IoT Network Security

The network security requirements for IoT differ from those for standard networks, as the variety of communication protocols, standards, and device capabilities create significant problems and increase complexity.

It is mandatory to use firewalls and systems to isolate the network of a particular mining company from external interference, e.g. communication with external systems must go through anti-virus scanning and check for other malicious code or software.

To ensure network security, it is imperative to install systems to detect and prevent intrusion into the company's network.

IoT Security of the Application Programming Interface (API)

The technology which ensures the security of the API in IoT applications protects the integrity of the data when transferring them between end devices (sensors, etc.). It certifies the end devices and accordingly allows or blocks the transfer of data, allowing communication only between authorised devices, users and IoT applications.

It is also possible to have a functionality that monitors the detection of potential threats and attacks against the API.

Encryption Use

Encryption techniques are used in a specific IoT application and in the whole system at different layers and protocols. Depending on the parameters of the individual devices (sometimes insufficient sensor memory), there are different levels of encryption, decryption and re-encryption throughout the system.

End-to-end encryption is the most effective solution to prevent various attacks, but the hardware capabilities of the devices, which can create problems with their speed and performance, must be taken into consideration. At the same time, it is important to constantly monitor the proper management of the keys.

IoT applications use encryption, RSA, SHA256-based or hash-chain technologies that can protect data from theft or tampering.

Starting from the design stage of an IoT application, the terminal devices must be selected in such a way so as to ensure the transmission of sensitive data in a sufficiently secure and encrypted manner.

Cloud Security

For the most part, IoT applications use cloud services to store, process, and retrieve data. This suggests that when using a particular IoT application, the risks that may come from the cloud must also be anticipated.

If a public Cloud platform is used, it is possible to have malicious users in the cloud, who can threaten the confidential information related to a particular IoT application in the mining industry. In this case, data encryption by authorised devices and users is mandatory.

When using a large number of IoT applications and a corresponding increase in the number of sensors and functionalities, it is recommended that mining companies create their own cloud, which guarantees them a much higher degree of protection and security of the transmitted data.

IoT Security Analytics

The ultimate goal of all IoT applications in the mining industry is to create an autonomous system that requires minimal human intervention. For this reason, techniques or algorithms based on artificial intelligence (AI) are used to analyse the processing of information and communication on the IoT environment. These solutions add machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data processing to the IoT environment, providing predictive modelling and anomaly detection.

Security analysis of IoT applications and environments is also used to detect IoT-specific threats and attacks that are not identified by traditional security solutions.

Conclusion

The use of IoT applications allows access to information from anywhere at any time to any device via M2M communication. The transfer through an IoT environment allows data to communicate and share between electronic devices and translate them in the way we want.

IoT makes systems in the mining industry efficient by saving costs and energy, as physical objects are controlled and digitally

connected to a wireless infrastructure, allowing maximum automation and control.

At the same time, the large number and variety of IoT devices and communication protocols pose challenges to the collection, processing and management of data from all these devices in terms of security and protection. The use of wireless connectivity and cloud technologies in the IoT environment requires additional security measures.

The presented technologies for ensuring security in IoT applications, applicable in the mining industry, are a combination of traditional and new methods and technologies, which guarantee cybersecurity.

At the same time, the use of the security technologies should not hinder the operation of the IoT application, which may make it unacceptable for use due to delays and additional checks.

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